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WP2 – Foundations

D2.4 – ACCEPT system architecture description v2

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Glossary

Application Programming Interface	An Application Programming Interface is a connection between computers or between computer programs. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software.
Communication Protocol	A communication protocol is a system of rules that allows two or more entities of a communications system to transmit information via any kind of variation of a physical quantity. The protocol defines the rules, syntax, semantics and synchronization of communication and possible error recovery methods.
Component Diagram	In Unified Modelling Language, a component diagram depicts how components are wired together to form larger components or software systems. They are used to illustrate the structure of arbitrarily complex systems.
Deployment Requirements	Deployment requirements describe the desired configuration of a software system.
Functional Specification	A functional specification in software development is a textual description that specifies the functions that a system or component must perform.
Non-functional Specifications	Non-functional Specifications define system attributes such as security, reliability, performance, maintainability, scalability, and usability
Payload	In computing and telecommunications, the payload is the part of transmitted data that is the actual intended message.
Software Architecture	Software architecture refers to the fundamental structures of a software system and the discipline of creating such structures and systems. Each structure comprises software elements, relations among them, and properties of both elements and relations.
Software Component	An individual software component is a software package, a web service, a web resource, or a Component that encapsulates a set of related functions (or data).
Upwards flexibility	The increase of energy consumption in response to a demand response signal
Downwards flexibility	The decrease of energy consumption in response to a demand response signal

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
ATs	Aggregator Tools
ASE	ACCEPT Solution Emulator
BAM	Building Asset Manager
BDT	Building Digital Twin
BI	Business Intelligence
BIML	Building Information Management Layer
CADR	Community Asset Portfolio Registry
CDT	Consumer Digital Twin
CiDT	Citizen Digital Twin
DAM	District Asset Management
DEE	Demand Elasticity Estimator
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DIML	District Information Management Layer
DoA	Description of Action
DR	Demand Response
D-SRI	Dynamic SRI Performance Rating
EC	European Commission
ECTs	Energy Community Tools
ECFM	Energy Community Flexibility Manager
EFT	Energy Flexibility Transactions
ESCo	Energy Service Company
ETs	ESCo Tools
EU	European Union
FFC	Flexibility Forecast Collection
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air-Conditioning
H-ECTs	Horizontal Energy Community Tools
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ODFM	On-Demand Flexibility Management
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
P2P-EP	P2P Exchange Platform
PMCD	Portfolio Monitoring and Control Dispatch

RTs	Retailer Tools
SCP	Smart Contract Platform
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
WP	Work Package
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

The following naming conventions have been adopted for the ACCEPT architecture:

- The District Asset Management component has been renamed to District Asset Manager. A new component, namely the District Information Management Layer (which is the equivalent to the BIML for district assets) has been introduced to cover the functionalities of the District Asset Data Connector.
- The tools of the Citizen Application covering all the functionalities described in the DoA are the Building Monitoring and Control Module, the Notification and Alerting System, the Collaboration Forum Module, the Statistical Analysis Module and the Optimal Energy Schedule and Recommendation module.
- The Horizontal Energy Community Tools are supported by the registries and repositories described in the DoA and their functionalities are included as specifications for the components VPP Manager, Demand Elasticity Estimator, Energy Community Flexibility Manager and the P2P Supply Shadow Administrator.

Executive summary

This report presents the work carried out in Task 2.3 of ACCEPT regarding the system architecture design process and results up to the date of submission of the second version of the deliverable. In particular, the deliverable includes the high-level architecture model of the complete system, with the initial point being the design as presented in the Description of Work, and further refined and updated based on the work carried out in this period. This high-level architecture has also been mapped to the various SGAM layers to assist the future integration and development activities.

The main bulk of the document concentrates on detailing the specifications and characteristics of the various system's software components. A dedicated template was created and circulated to all relevant partners in order to provide the components' functional and non-functional specifications, highlight interdependencies with other components, and declare the input/output data requirements (Annex I – Component's Specifications and Requirements Template). Additionally, detailed component diagrams were created, and finally, the connection with Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1) was performed via a mapping of components to Use Cases that required relevant functionalities. Sequence diagrams were already created for D2.1 and are not presented here.

A new section was created for the second version of the deliverable; it includes an update of the Use Cases, as described in D2.1, following necessary refinements and modifications that occurred in the course of the project. Similarly, the SGAM mapping, the component description and diagrams were updated to reflect the advances of the project.

This is the second and final version of ACCEPT's system architecture. It will drive the development of the second and final iteration of the system and its constituent components. Following that, further refinements, if necessary, will be integrated in the new versions of the different components of the project.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope of the Deliverable

The scope of the present deliverable is to present the work carried out in the context of Task 2.3 of ACCEPT project. More precisely, it is focused on the system architecture design process up to the detailed functional and non-functional specifications of each system component, also including the high-level and conceptual architecture models of the complete system. The ACCEPT system conceptual architecture was briefly presented in the Description of Action (DoA) and was further updated based on work carried out during this period with the involvement of all relevant technology providers. This high-level architecture has also been mapped to the various SGAM layers in order to assist the future integration and development activities.

The main part of the document is focused on a detailed presentation of the system's software components. The functional and non-functional specifications of the components, their interdependencies with other components and the required input/output data for each of them, were provided from all relevant partners, through a dedicated template that was created and circulated among them. In addition, detailed component diagrams were created and linked to Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1), correlating each component to relevant Use Cases (UCs) and describing relevant functionalities for each of them.

1.2. Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 provides information on the scope of the deliverable, its structure and the dependencies that exist between the relevant task and current deliverable and other project tasks and deliverables.
- Chapter 2 described the methodological process adopted, and presents the high-level system architecture, the conceptual ACCEPT architecture and its mapping to the SGAM model. It also provides a short description and the updated sequence diagrams of the project use cases, which have been refined since the submission of Deliverable 2.1 based on feedback received by consortium members and the developments of the preliminary versions of the technical solutions;
- Chapter 3 presents the detailed (non-)functional specifications, interdependencies, UC correlation, implementation view and input/output requirements of the system's constituent components;
- Chapter 4 concludes this document and includes key lessons learned; and,
- Annex I includes the component characterization template.

1.3. Interdependencies with Other Tasks and Deliverables

The deliverable reports on activities that have been performed in the context of "T2.3 System architecture design, configuration & elaboration (M4-M18)", with main outcome the second version of ACCEPT's system architecture. It accompanies and heavily depends on the work performed in T2.1 of the project and its associated deliverable "D2.1 ACCEPT business scenarios, use cases & requirements". The second version of the project's architecture includes a refinement of the Use Cases (UCs) (section 2.2). The work carried out here drives the development of the first prototype of the software components in WP4 and WP5, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ACCEPT Work Package interdependency Graph

1.4. Difference between D2.3 and D2.4

Deliverable 2.4 as the second version of the Accept System Architecture Description includes all updates that have been made to the various elements of the ACCEPT architecture since the release of the first version (D2.3, submitted in M10 of the project). These updates were driven by necessary refinements of the components of the ACCEPT solution and/or advances of the project.

Specifically, the main updates concern the following elements:

ACCEPT system conceptual architecture

The high-level architecture of the ACCEPT system has been further refined to include the main interfaces and data exchanges among the solution components and subcomponents, as well as component-level databases and user interfaces.

UCs

Each UC was discussed between concerned partners who provided updates on the progress of the components of the project and suggested minor modifications to the UC where necessary. For instance, in UC6 residential EVs are not applicable, as it was not possible to incorporate such technologies in the pilot sites of the project. Following this, the UML diagrams of each UC was updated to reflect eventual modifications.

SGAM mapping

In the first version of the deliverable, two out of the five different SGAM layers were analysed, namely the information and communication layers. The second and final version of the architecture deliverable, based on the outputs of WP2, WP4 and WP5 in year 2 of the project (e.g., business scenarios, preliminary versions of technical solutions, etc.), delivers the remaining three layers of the SGAM framework, namely the component, business and function layers.

Components specifications and requirements

Responsible partners for each component / layer made the necessary changes that were then reviewed and discussed by concerned partners. Relevant UCs per component were updated, along with input/output data and actions. Respectively, the new versions of the component diagrams are provided. A new section, dedicated to the business intelligence and user interface system of the Energy Community toolset, has been added to the relevant section.

Lessons learned

The final version of the system architecture deliverable includes key learning points derived mainly from the process of defining and designing the main system components, their interfaces and specifications. They mainly concern best practices on the design of integrated system architecture models and the development of components comprising an integrated system that will be tested under controlled and real-life environments.

2. ACCEPT System Architecture

2.1. Methodological Framework

The initial step towards defining ACCEPT's system architecture and providing the required specifications for the development of the necessary components has been the analysis of T2.1 results. The scope of T2.1 has been the extraction of the end-user requirements, as well as the creation of the business and use cases of the project. With the user requirements and Use Cases (UC) elicitation being the scope of T2.1, upon which the system functionalities and architecture are then constructed, it is worth mentioning that within D2.1, each UC was described not only via a textual and a Unified Markup Language (UML) UC diagram, but also through a sequence diagram detailing the interactions between the different components. Therefore, the two documents must be seen as complementary to each other in their content and purpose. Furthermore, during the course of the project, the UC diagrams were refined to reflect the advancement of the project and subsequent modifications. The updated UML diagrams of the UCs are presented in this document (Section 2.2), as a new version of D2.1 is not envisaged.

As mentioned before, upon the finalisation of the UCs' definition and the submission of D2.1, the work pertaining T2.3 was initiated. Here, the first step was the provision of a robust and concrete methodology, based on which the technical partners could derive the necessary information for the subsequent development tasks, considering the requirements derived by the aforementioned analysis. The steps of the adopted methodology included the followings:

1. Analysis of UCs for extraction of functional requirements and validation of responsible components/contributing partners;
2. Introduction to necessary concepts and tools for the creation of the UML component diagrams. The online free suite diagrams.net was adopted for the generation of the diagrams. Hypertech performed a short tutorial call with other partners to introduce the tool;
3. Generation of the component characterization template, which incorporated all fields identified as necessary for the accumulation of the required information; the template was created by Hypertech and was distributed to all involved partners, along with instructions for properly filling in the required information;
4. Creation of the high-level system architecture by Hypertech, which was distributed to all partners; along with the characterisation templates;
5. Collection of filled in templates, consolidation, and evaluation of the content;
6. Second iteration of the components' characterisation, in order to align interdependencies between components and verify that all required functionalities are considered; and finally
7. Refinement of the high-level system architecture and creation of the SGAM mapping.

The abovementioned steps led to the release of the preliminary version of the ACCEPT system architecture. The preliminary system architecture was then the basis for the development of the various system components. The development of these components and the integration of them into a single module provided useful feedback with regards to the component functional specifications and the required interfaces among components. This feedback was then incorporated in the final version of the architecture.

Through the elicitation of the system architecture and the further discussions on requirements introduced by the project use cases with the consortium members, the need to refine and evolve the use cases was identified. As a result, a series of technical workshops (incl. a workshop held during the 3rd project General Assembly meeting) among consortium members was organised culminated in the refinement of the project use cases.

In the following sections, we present the results of this process, starting from the refined use cases, the high-level and conceptual system architecture diagrams, and then moving on to the individual software components.

2.2. Updated Use Cases UML diagrams

UCs are crucial for the design, development and implementation of the project's solutions as well as the demonstration campaign. Based on a meticulous methodology (described in detail in D2.1), the ACCEPT consortium, and specifically the partners working on the development of the project's tools, have identified fourteen UCs. These UCs describe and define the key processes and functionalities of the developed solutions.

During the course of the project, refinements were made to the initial UCs, either driven by modifications of the project activities or ameliorations that the consortium deemed necessary. These refinements are presented in this section. Each UC was thoroughly discussed in small circles, concerned partners presenting new elements and eventual new requirements (since D2.1 and M8) and agreeing on the necessary adjustments to the UCs.

Thirteen UCs are presented in the following section, including updated versions of UML diagrams. UC14 "Active Citizen and LEC Engagement" has no technical implementation and therefore is out of scope of this deliverable.

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

2.2.1. UC1 Monitoring and Visualization of Metering & Sensor Energy Data in community buildings

Description

The scope of UC1 is to enable collection of high-quality metering and sensing data from a modular and interoperable IoT gateway platform that will also allow for secure communication across actors and components. Furthermore, this UC provides data visualization means for more efficient communication of events, behaviours and profiles that will allow for deeper understanding.

Specifically, the UC enables citizens participating in the ACCEPT trials to access and visualise information regarding the house ambient conditions, the performance of their appliances and their total energy consumption. Energy communities also have access to such information for monitoring the Energy Performance Contracting KPIs of their buildings. They could also visualise such data, if required, through the Energy Community Platform.

This use case will examine the high value achieved by providing an integrated solution that can be assembled from market available components, act as a hub for off-the-self sensors, meters and actuators, and be compatible for all building types. Depending on the building, different sensors may be needed that need to be integrated into the system.

UML diagram

UC1 Monitoring and Visualization of Metering & Sensor Energy Data in community buildings

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

2.2.2. UC2 Building self-consumption employing Virtual Thermal Energy Storage optimization

Description

This UC establishes an optimization framework for the maximisation of self-generated energy. It enables the optimal scheduling of heating/cooling household appliances/devices, combined with the inherit heating storage capability of a building (thermal inertia and/or hot water tank), with the aim of increasing the consumption of self-generated renewable energy via renewable resources (PVs). As a result, the UC also results in the minimisation of prosumers' dependence from the grid and consequently of their energy bill, by covering their consumption with local green energy and making them self-sufficient.

UML diagram

* The training of the CIDT and BDT models is carried out in alignment with the process described in D4.9 and Figures 2 and 4.

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

2.2.3. UC3 Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting and optimisation taking into account comfort boundaries, activity patterns and possible requirements

Description

The scope of this UC is to forecast the available flexibility of a prosumer, considering the comfort and convenience of the prosumer, so that any optimal scheduling of appliances' operation does not hinder those. It provides intra-day and day-ahead forecasts of flexibility, based on the energy resources installed in the premises and translates flexibility requests to the building into scheduling operations for the electricity resources in the building/apartment/thermal zones.

Comfort boundaries and activities patterns of prosumers are calculated by the Citizen Digital Twin based on data collected from house appliances and sensors. The intricacies of each building and of the appliances within it are also considered for the calculation of available flexibility, as well as weather and indoor ambient conditions. Requirements set by the implementation of service scenarios (e.g., cost optimisation, heating-as-a-service) are also considered, when applicable, for the calculation of the available flexibility of a prosumer.

UML diagram

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

UC3 Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting and optimisation taking into account comfort boundaries, activity patterns and possible requirements

* The training of the CIDT and BDT models is carried out in alignment with the process described in D4.9 and Figures 2 and 4.

2.2.4. UC4 Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation and analysis in community level

Description

The UC focuses on calculating, at community/portfolio level, the demand elasticity, i.e., the degree in the change of energy demand when there is a change in energy prices. The aim is for the likes of Retailers to use demand elasticity for the design of dynamic energy tariffs, which can then be used for an implicit demand-response scenario.

UML diagram

UC4 Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation and analysis in community level

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

2.2.5. UC5 Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management for community self-balancing

Description

This UC concerns the management of district-level assets to provide them with flexibility capabilities based on forecasting and local control optimization. To do so, it takes into account available Distributed Energy Resources at District level, weather forecast and energy pricing; it then forecasts mid-term (intra-day) and short-term (hour ahead) generation, to provide the best load/generation distribution, while considering the economic impact caused by the dynamic pricing scheme. It should be noted that, at the moment, there is no EV charger at district level available for participation in the project, however we expect that a V2G enabled charger will be added to the Swiss trials within ACCEPT. As such, UC5 foresees data from EV chargers.

UML diagram

2.2.6. UC6 Day-ahead smart charging flexibility via EV usage pattern profiling and forecasting

Description

This UC focuses on calculating, on a day-ahead basis, the flexibility available from EVs participating in the project. The forecasted flexibility considers the EV usage and charging patterns of the EV driver, their preferences and requirements. UC6 creates EV charging profiles, then extracts the forecast of EV charging and finally calculates the associated potential flexibility. EV charging is expected to represent an important (and increasing) share of the electricity consumption, it is also however dispatchable, and can therefore prove very useful in demand-side management schemes, particularly when large numbers of electric cars are considered, as can be the case with energy communities. It should be noted that, at the moment, there is no EV charger at district level available for participation in the project, however we expect that a V2G enabled charger will be added to the Swiss trials within ACCEPT. As such, UC6 foresees data from EV chargers.

UML diagram

UC6 Day-ahead smart charging flexibility via EV usage pattern profiling and forecasting

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

2.2.7. UC7 Community-level P2P flexibility/energy exchange based on locally produced renewable energy

Description

UC7 enables the participation in a community level P2P flexibility/energy exchange platform based on locally produced renewable energy in order to collectively achieve demand and supply optimization. This UC examines the benefits of fair, transparent and optimal energy/flexibility exchange between peers on a community level utilizing both private and district assets. At the same time, it allows the community to facilitate various business models (trading, collective self-consumption etc.)

Based on consumption and production forecasts, retailer's buy and sell prices and grid tariffs, a universal P2P energy price is formed for internal trading inside the community. Every 15 minutes P2P market will run, and trading will be secured through Smart Contracts and blockchain technology. Exchange/transaction costs are minimised, in an effort to promote collaboration between community members, while data privacy is enhanced, leading to increased trust among trading parties.

UML diagram

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

UC7 Community-level P2P flexibility/energy exchange based on locally produced renewable energy

* Smart Contract
 **Community level
 ***Results from UC13

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

2.2.8. UC8 Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes

Description

When a DR event is triggered by the DSO, this UC requests flexibility information (potential) at prosumer and community level and proposes appropriate sequence of actions and collaboration among the available tools for the calculation and implementation of an optimal operational schedule of all available controllable assets. It therefore provides optimal DR solutions at community level, depending on the agreed role, i.e. Aggregator, Retailer, ESCo, based on inputs such as demand/generation flexibility.

UML diagram

2.2.9. UC9 Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes

Description

UC9 decides how to provide flexibility (i.e., which devices and for how long), based on dynamic network energy tariff and the flexibility forecast at prosumer and community level. In this case, the trigger for the DR event is the market electricity price. Hence, the most appropriate sequence of actions and collaboration among the available tools is established, in order in both end-user and community levels to participate in an implicit DR event.

UML diagram

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

2.2.10. UC10 Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service

Description

UC10 enables the assessment of the grid state and, upon identification of congestion problems, triggers the dispatch of all available flexible assets within the community portfolio (i.e., both building-level and district-level assets). In this case, the community acts as an Aggregator, bundling together the flexibility available from its portfolio and using it for resolving identified grid problems. The UC provides the real-time status of the network (through the ASE module, which, as in the case of UC8, assesses whether or not there is congestion on the networks and determines the required actions to solve it), but also forecasts congestion events from demand/generation forecasting.

UML diagram

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

UC10 Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service

D2.4 – ACCEPT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION V2

2.2.11. UC11 Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration for aggregated portfolio balancing

Description

UC11 is tightly related to the demand elasticity forecasting UC (UC4). Using the information on community-level demand elasticity, as well as information on possible portfolio-level imbalances, the Retailer calculates an optimal pricing scheme that will then be communicated to their customers downstream. Though elasticity, forecasting and aggregation, the energy supplier is facilitated to avoid imbalances and to encourage consumers to proceed with the new dynamic pricing schemas. The UC is quite similar to UC9, however emphasis is given on the calculation of an implicit price by the ASE based on the state of the grid.

UML diagram

UC11 Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration for aggregated portfolio balancing

2.2.12. UC12 Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management

Description

UC12 concerns the optimal operation of available heating systems at District level (both centralised and distributed). It provides adaptive scheduling for each heating asset in order to obtain maximum savings while preserving the proper operating point during peak demand. The following factors are considered: estimation of heating demand, output temperature, internal temperature setpoints, ambient temperature prediction & electricity market prices. The UC depends heavily on the availability of controllable district-level heating loads. Should no such loads exist, the UC will need to either not be implemented or tested under simulation scenarios.

UML diagram

UC12 Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management

2.2.13. UC13 Increase self-consumption at community level

Description

The scope of this UC is to allow energy communities to maximize the use of their renewable resources, as it aligns energy demand with local renewable generation. It focuses on the optimisation of heating/cooling and other flexible and controllable devices at district/community level, so that energy generated by renewable DERs is not wasted but utilised optimally to satisfy the user needs and reduce the amount of purchased energy from the grid. The Energy Community Flexibility Manager collects optimised values of production and consumption from both buildings and district assets and flexibility is exploited collectively by the Community Tools.

UML diagram

2.3. High-Level and Conceptual System Architecture

ACCEPT’s high-level system architecture can be seen in Figure 1. It was derived from the initial description of the ACCEPT solution and its components in the DoA, further refined and updated to cover any new requirements and reflect the work performed in WP2. Arrows in the diagram indicate functional and/or data dependencies from the source packages to the pointed packages.

Figure 2. ACCEPT high-level system architecture

The main composite components of the ACCEPT system have remained largely unchanged, both in terms of naming (slight adjustments have been made for consistency and accuracy reasons) and in terms of general functionalities, from their descriptions in the DoA. Below we shortly restate the main objectives of each such part of the system. For extended information on all the components, the reader is directed to the next chapter.

- **Building Information Management Layer (BIML):** It is responsible for capturing live information streams from a host of sensors, meters and actuators in the building, pre-process the data, perform disaggregation, prepare semantically-enhanced information for the following components and facilitate the downstream communication of control commands. One of the main roles of this component is ensuring data security.
- **District Information Management Layer (DIML):** It is responsible for capturing live information streams from available district-level assets owned by the communities taking part in the project, pre-process data, perform disaggregation, prepare semantically-enhanced information for other ACCEPT solution components and facilitate downstream communication of control actions.
- **District Asset Management (DAM):** It includes the functionalities for monitoring, control and management of district-level assets (e.g., photovoltaic (PV) panels, Electric Vehicle (EV) charging, storage, heat pumps) to enable their integration in the Virtual Power Plant that encapsulates all energy assets under the direct control of the energy community (or within the portfolio managed by the market actor) and whose flexibility can be leveraged for the business objectives of the community.
- **Building Asset Manager (BAM):** This composite component wraps all components related to management and analysis of building-derived data. It includes the On-Demand Flexibility Management (ODFM), which is responsible for consumer/building-level optimizations, the Consumer Digital Twin, which provides mathematical models of the building and the citizens-residents' preferences, as well as the Dynamic SRI Performance Rating, which is responsible for quantifying and updating the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI).
- **Community-Level P2P Exchange Platform (P2P-EP):** It is a blockchain-based and smart-contract-enabled platform to facilitate the exchange of energy or flexibility between the community members for individual consumer or community level optimization.
- **Citizen Application (C-App):** They offer desirable functionalities to citizens through energy and non-energy services (e.g., convenience, security, ambient assisted living features) based on the infrastructure and background services necessary for the provision of demand response services from buildings in order to enhance the value proposition of the ACCEPT.
- **Energy Community Tools (ECTs):** They are a collection of tools that enable the energy community to collectively manage the assets at hand as either of three market roles: retailer, Energy Service Company (ESCO) or aggregator – or any combination of these. These tools facilitate Virtual Power Plant management for consolidation and optimal use of available flexibility in markets or retailer operations as well as energy self-consumption optimization at the community level.

In the following figure, the high-level system architecture has been enriched with information on available user interfaces and component-level databases, as well as further information on data exchanges among components and, in the case of the Energy Communities Tools, sub-components of the ACCEPT solution.

Figure 3. ACCEPT system conceptual architecture

2.4. SGAM mapping

2.4.1. SGAM Introduction

As stated in T2.3, one of the goals is to present a mapping of the system architecture on the SGAM model, so as to promote reusability and also enable comparisons with the system architectures proposed by other BRIDGE projects. SGAM was introduced by the Smart Grid Coordination Group “as a methodology for describing smart grid use cases and services with an architectural approach. This methodology allows a neutral representation of the

involved technologies highlighting their interoperability supported by standards and, consequently, enabling standards gap analysis¹. SGAM’s first level of abstraction consists of five interoperable layers:

- The **business layer** represents the business view on the information exchange
- The **function layer** describes functions and services including their relationships from an architectural viewpoint
- The **information layer** describes the information that is being used and exchanged between functions, services and components.
- The **communication layer** describes protocols and mechanisms for the interoperable exchange of information between components
- The **component layer** shows the physical distribution of participating components in the smart grid context.

It has to be stressed that SGAM offers further classification properties within each layer, effectively providing a three-dimensional architectural model. For the stated purposes though, it was deemed sufficient to perform only the first level mapping of ACCEPT’s system architecture.

2.4.2. Mapping System Architecture to the SGAM model

Figure 3 and Figure 4 restate the ACCEPT system architecture, but this time under the perspective of the Communication and Information layers of SGAM, respectively. Each component is placed over the relevant area of the SGAM plane. To improve readability of the figures, sub-components of the ACCEPT solution have been removed. Furthermore, high level information about connections between the composite components have been provided. Details about each connection are provided in Section 3.

Figure 4. ACCEPT system architecture - SGAM Communication Layer mapping

¹ Estebasari, Abouzar & Barbierato, Luca & Bahmanyar, Alireza & Bottaccioli, Lorenzo & Macii, Enrico & Patti, Edoardo. (2019). A SGAM-Based Test Platform to Develop a Scheme for Wide Area Measurement-Free Monitoring of Smart Grids under High PV Penetration. Energies. 12. 1417. 10.3390/en12081417.

Figure 5. ACCEPT system architecture - SGAM Information Layer mapping

These figures provide a solid basis for the ACCEPT-to-SGAM mapping process.

Since the preliminary version of the architecture deliverable, further clarity with regards to the technical use cases to be tested under the framework of ACCEPT has been achieved. Business scenarios that will be investigated at the four pilot sites of the project have been fully defined as part of the WP2 activities. Finally, the preliminary versions of the ACCEPT solution components have been largely developed, allowing the refinement of the system architecture based on preliminary user feedback (mainly on the user interfaces of the project) and test results. Based on those refinements and advancements, the remaining three SGAM layers – the component, business and function layers – of the ACCEPT solution are provided in the figures below.

Figure 6. ACCEPT system architecture - SGAM Component Layer mapping

Each of the components included in the component layer of the ACCEPT SGAM comprises of various sub-components, presented in more detail and analysed in the next section of this document.

Figure 7. ACCEPT system architecture - SGAM Business Layer mapping

The Business Layer of the ACCEPT SGAM has been largely based on the business scenarios and services developed under the framework of Task 2.5. The diagram also includes the main actors involved in each business process implemented by the different solution components.

Figure 8. ACCEPT system architecture – SGAM Function Layer mapping

The function layer of the SGAM describes the main functions implemented by the solution components as part of the 13 technical use cases demonstrated at the project pilot sites. These functions are further detailed as part of the functional specifications of each ACCEPT solution component.

3. ACCEPT Components’ Specifications and Requirements

In this chapter we present the filled in templates of all identified components comprising the ACCEPT software system. The original template, along with guidelines/clarifications on what exactly information should be filled in in each field can be found in Annex I – Component’s Specifications and Requirements Template. Each section in this chapter is named after one of the six composite components of the ACCEPT system. Within, subsections, if any, correspond to the main constituent components respectively.

3.1. Building Information Management Layer – BIML

General Information	
Component name	Building Information Management Layer (BIML)
Component Description	<p>BIML is the component responsible for interfacing with the real world, by collecting metering, sensing and monitoring data from the physical assets of the building and processing it for further use from other components. It is a combination of a software and a hardware system.</p> <p>The hardware part consists of an IoT gateway that enables bidirectional interoperable communication between building’s sensors, meters and actuators and the rest of the ACCEPT system components. The software stack allows for the continuous processing of the live data streams by a smart ingestion engine.</p> <p>The BIML follows a multilayer architecture, consisting of five main layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Security Layer is responsible for preserving data security and enforcing information access control to other components. • In the Data Ingestion Layer, data from IoT infrastructures is ingested into a queue of messages to be processed before being permanently stored in the BIML data repository. Data ingestions are delivered as messages through message-brokers to ensure stability, delivery consistency, fault-tolerance transmission, asynchronous communication between services, increasing reliability and system performance. • In the Application Layer, data stored in the BIML data repository or directly received from the message brokers are divided into small batches and sent for processing; applications for real-time data-processing (e.g., cleansing, normalising) are included in this layer. • The Data Management Layer provides a common storage cloud infrastructure, accommodating all the building level IoT and EV data. • The Data Modelling Integration Layer hosts the IoT and EV static and stream data mapping to the BIML internal data models.
Interfaces with End-Users	None

Relevant UCs	UC1, UC2, UC7, UC8, UC9, UC10, UC13	
Lead Developing Partner	QUE	
Programming Languages	Java, Scala	
Deployment Requirements	Physical components require manual installation in premises. For the Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) design and installation, audits of pilot sites are required. The IoT data ingestion and processing will be deployed as a cloud service.	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	1. Establish connection with meters, sensors and actuators	
	2. Receive device status and data streams	
	3. Enable dispatching of control commands	
	4. Protect sensible and private data	
	5. Cleanse incoming stream of data	
	6. Perform data Normalization and/or Aggregation	
	7. Perform non-intrusive load monitoring	
	8. Store data locally	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Generate Control Actions for activation of flexibility	Building Asset Manager
Non-functional Specifications	1. Scalability – integration of a large number of devices	
	2. Robustness and error reporting	
	3. Interoperability to enable communication with a variety of sensing, metering and actuating devices.	
Implementation View		
Component Diagram	<p>The diagram illustrates the system architecture. On the left, 'Building IoT infrastructure' and 'External legacy system' provide 'IoT data' and 'Weather data' to the 'BIML' (Building Information Modeling Language) block. The BIML block consists of five layers: Security Layer, Data Ingestion Layer, Application Layer, Data Management Layer, and Data Modeling Integration Layer. The BIML block sends 'Control actions' back to the infrastructure and legacy system. On the right, BIML sends 'IoT data, weather data' to 'BAM' (Building Asset Manager), which in turn sends 'Control actions' back to BIML. BIML also sends 'Metering IoT data' to 'P2P-EP' (Peer-to-Peer Energy Platform) and 'IoT data' to 'C-App' (Control Application), which sends 'Control actions' back to BIML.</p>	
	Interfaces/Data Requirements	

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	IoT data ²	Building IoT infrastructure	JSON	AMQP
	Weather data	External legacy system	JSON	RESTful
	Control actions	Building Asset Manager	JSON	AMQP
	Control actions	Citizen App	JSON	AMQP
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	IoT data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Weather data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Metering IoT data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	IoT data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Control actions	Building IoT infrastructure	JSON	RESTful

3.2. District Information Management Layer – DIML

General Information	
Component name	District Information Management Layer (DIML)
Component Description	<p>Similar to the BIML for building-level assets, the DIML enables bidirectional communication with district-level DER elements, incl. generation, storage and demand district-level assets.</p> <p>The DIML `s software consists of five main layers, identical to the layers of BIML for the district-level assets monitoring, metering and sensing data management (see Section 3.1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Security layer; • the Data Ingestion layer; • the Application layer; • the Data Management layer; and • the Data Modelling Integration layer.

² IoT data include metering, sensing and monitoring data from downstream (low-level) IoT infrastructure. More specifically, metering data refer to data gathering by metering devices (such as smart clamps and smart meters), sensing data refer to ambient condition data gathered through sensors, and monitoring data refer to data obtained from the actuators/controllers of the IoT infrastructure.

Interfaces with End-users	Citizens (through citizen app)	
Relevant UCs	UC5, UC6, UC7, UC8, UC10, UC12	
Lead Developing Partner	CIRCE	
Programming Languages	C++, Python	
Deployment Requirements	Physical component(s) that require(s) deployment at the demo site (the district-level IoT infrastructure).	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	1. Establish connection with meters, sensors and actuators	
	2. Receive device status and data streams	
	3. Enable dispatching of control commands	
	4. Protect sensible and private data	
	5. Cleanse incoming stream of data	
	6. Perform data Normalization and/or Aggregation	
	7. Receive weather data	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Generate Control Actions for activation of flexibility from district-level DERs	District Asset Manager (DAM)
Non-functional Specifications	Secure communications	
	Scalability – integration of a large number of devices	
	Robustness and error reporting	
	Interoperability to enable communication with a variety of sensing, metering and actuating devices.	
Implementation View		
Component Diagram	<p>The diagram illustrates the system architecture. On the left, 'District-level IoT infrastructure' sends 'Metering and monitoring IoT data' to the 'DIML' block. The 'DIML' block consists of five layers: Security Layer, Data Ingestion Layer, Application Layer, Data Management Layer, and Data Modeling Integration Layer. From the DIML, 'Control actions, Dispatch Schedule' are sent to the 'DAM' (District Asset Manager). 'Metering data' is sent to 'ECTs' (Energy Control Transformers), and 'EV related data' is sent to 'C-App' (Citizen App). There is also a bidirectional flow of 'Control actions' between the District-level IoT infrastructure and the DIML.</p>	
Interfaces/Data Requirements		

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	Monitoring and metering IoT data	Available district-level IoT infrastructure	JSON	RESTful
	Control actions	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Dispatch schedule	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Data	To		Communication protocol
Output	Control actions	Available district-level IoT infrastructure	TBD ³	TBD
	Metering and monitoring IoT data, weather data, EV data	District Asset Manager	JSON	MQTT
	Metering IoT data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	MQTT
	EV related data	Citizen App	JSON	MQTT

3.3. District Asset Manager – DAM

General Information	
Component name	District Asset Manager (DAM)
Component Description	<p>The DAM retrieves information on available district-level assets from the DIML and generates forecasts of their operation, which are then passed to the energy community tools for consideration under various community-wide optimisation scenarios (such as community-wide self-consumption). The DAM is also responsible for receiving optimisation requests from the energy community tools and translating them into control actions for the DIML.</p> <p>The DAM comprises three main sub-components, namely the Generation Forecasting Module, the Storage Forecasting Module and the Demand Forecasting Module, responsible for the generation of forecasts for generation, storage and demand district-level assets respectively. The</p>

³ This is purposely left undefined, as there are still ongoing discussions with the Swiss pilot partner on the availability of controllable district-level heating loads.

	Storage Forecasting Module is also responsible for performing district-level optimisations and generating control actions for district-level assets based on the results of such optimisations.	
Interfaces with End-users	None	
Relevant UCs	UC5, UC8, UC10, UC12, UC13	
Lead Developing Partner	CIRCE	
Programming Language(s)	Ada, Go, C++, Python	
Deployment Requirements	Deployment in the cloud. The installation of the DIML in the relevant pilot sites.	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	1. Forecast district-level generation	
	2. Forecast district-level demand (demand from district-level loads/assets, such as district-level heat pumps)	
	3. Forecast district-level storage capacity and usage based on information on load and generation, as well as dynamic pricing	
	4. Create demand flexibility forecasts (upwards/downwards) for storage and demand assets	
	5. Generate control actions for district-level assets	
	6. Retrieve weather data	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Monitor district-level devices	District Information Management Layer
	Apply control timeseries	District Information Management Layer
	Optimize community self-consumption	Energy Community Tools
	Apply portfolio DR request	Energy Community Tools
Non-functional Specifications	Secure communications	
Implementation View		

Interfaces/Data Requirements

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	Metering and monitoring IoT data	District Information Management Layer	JSON	MQTT
	EV related data	District Information Management Layer	JSON	MQTT
	Optimisation requests	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecasting requests	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful
	Weather data	External legacy system	JSON	RESTful
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	Control actions	District Information Management Layer	JSON	MQTT
	Optimisation results	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecast	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful

3.4. Building Asset Manager – BAM

The Building Asset Manager (BAM) wraps the various components that are deployed at building level, in particular the On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM) and the Consumer Digital Twin (CDT). As such, it suffices to characterize its constituent parts.

3.4.1. On Demand Flexibility Manager – ODFM

General Information

Component name	On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM)
Component Description	<p>The ODFM constitutes the optimisation and control dispatch engine within the Building Asset Manager and comprises the Flexibility Forecasting Module, the Self-consumption Forecasting Module and the Control Management and Dispatch Module. In summary, the component will provide the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility forecasting, where the baseline consumption of a single prosumer is calculated, as well as their available upwards and downwards flexibility, considering their comfort preferences and consumption behaviour; • Self-consumption scenarios optimisation, aiming to schedule the use of resources in such a way that as much self-generated energy is consumed during the day; • Energy/cost explicit Demand Response (DR) scenarios optimisation, where the baseline and alternative possible timeseries of electricity consumption (which are then bundled as offered flexibility) are calculated by solving optimization problems with different objective functions and comfort constraints' formulations; • Cost optimisation scenarios, including ToU tariff and implicit DR scenarios, where the main objective of the optimisation problem is to minimise the energy cost for the prosumer, based on time-varying energy prices; • Comfort-as-a-Service scenarios, where the optimisation of relevant appliances' operation ensures that the occupant stays at maximum comfort within the day; and • Control dispatch, for breaking down a DR request and computing the necessary control actions for the building assets. <p>A local repository within the ODFM will be collecting and storing the data and control demands from the BIML, which will then be utilised for performing optimisations.</p>
Interfaces with End-users	None
Relevant UCs	UC2, UC3, UC8, UC9, UC10, UC12
Lead Developing Partner	Hypertech
Programming Languages	Python, Java

Deployment Requirements	Deployed as a cloud service. Requires installation of the BIML at the relevant pilot sites and adequate historical IoT data for the Consumer Digital Twin (CDT) models training.	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	1. Build baseline optimisation system	
	2. Build extended comfort optimisation	
	3. Forecast environmental conditions	
	4. Minimize energy bought from the grid	
	5. Minimize cost of purchased energy from the grid	
	6. Maximize consumption of self-generated energy	
	7. Compile Flexibility timeseries	
	8. Translate devices' consumption timeseries to control timeseries	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Model building residents' occupancy	Consumer Digital Twin
	Model building residents' comfort	Consumer Digital Twin
	Model building thermal spaces	Consumer Digital Twin
	Model building Heating, Ventilation and Air-Conditioning (HVAC) systems	Consumer Digital Twin
	Model building Domestic Hot Water (DHW) systems	Consumer Digital Twin
	Model building generation (renewables), EVs and Stationary Battery systems	Consumer Digital Twin
	Retrieve raw data	Building Information Management Layer
	Monitor devices	Building Information Management Layer
	Apply control timeseries	Building Information Management Layer
	Optimize community self-consumption	Energy Community Tools
Apply portfolio DR request	Energy Community Tools	
Non-functional Specifications	1. Raw data and control commands securely transferred to/from BIML and stored	
	2. One ODFM active for each pilot building	
	3. Self-consumption optimization and/or Flexibility forecasting provided either on demand or on a scheduled basis	
Implementation View		

Interfaces/Data Requirements

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	Profiling data ⁴	Consumer Digital Twin	JSON	RESTful
	Fitted building thermal model	Consumer Digital Twin	JSON	RESTful
	Fitted DER models ⁵	Consumer Digital Twin	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation requests	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful
	IoT data	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful
	Weather data	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	Profiling data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful or AMQP

⁴ Profiling data include occupancy profiles, comfort profiles, citizen lifestyle and activity patterns, and EV profiles (e.g., mobility habits, such as driving and charging patterns).

⁵ DER models may include HVAC, DHW, EV, storage and PV models (depending on building-level device availability at pilot sites).

Optimisation results	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
Profiling data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
Control actions	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful or AMQP

3.4.2. Consumer Digital Twin – CDT

General Information	
Component name	Consumer Digital Twin (CDT)
Component Description	<p>The Consumer Digital Twin (CDT) component is responsible for exposing the main modelling functionalities to the rest of the BAM components. It consists of three main subcomponents, namely the Citizen Digital Twin (CiDT), the Building Digital Twin (BDT) and the Dynamic Smart Readiness Indicator (D-SRI).</p> <p>The CiDT has as its main objective to mathematically capture the behavioural profiles of the building residents and provide an energy-related characterization of their habits. In essence, the component will perform the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn and forecast the occupancy patterns of the residents, • Identify the thermal comfort preferences of the end-users, • Estimate the demand patterns for usage of Domestic Hot Water (DHW), as well as for EV charging, if any is present, • Capture the price elasticity of demand for each household when variable tariff schemes are applied. <p>The BDT sits alongside the CiDT in order to provide the thermal modelling of the building envelope (thermal resistance and capacitance), as well as the characterization of any energy resources that are located within the building, both in terms of consuming loads (HVAC) as well as energy storage and generation systems. The models integrated in this system will be utilized for flexibility forecasting as well as translating DR requests to control dispatches.</p> <p>The D-SRI component is the third sub-component of CDT. Its purpose is to calculate in a dynamic fashion (time and resident dependent) an SRI-based Smart Readiness Indicator. To achieve this, the component will take advantage of the modelling capabilities of the other BAM components in order to periodically update appropriately selected/relevant metrics based on the streams of data at hand.</p>
Interfaces with End-users	None

Relevant UCs	UC2, UC3, UC13		
Lead Developing Partner	Hypertech		
Programming Languages	Python, Java		
Deployment Requirements	Deployed as a cloud service		
Specifications			
Functional Specifications	CiDT:		
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Model building residents' occupancy 2. Model building residents' comfort 3. Model building residents' demand patterns 4. Fit occupancy model 5. Fit comfort model 6. Retrieve environmental conditions and retail prices 7. Model user EV usage patterns 8. Fit elasticity regression model 9. Estimate consumer elasticity 		
	BDT:		
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Model building thermal spaces 2. Model building HVAC systems 3. Model building DHW systems 4. Model building generation (renewables) and Stationary Battery systems 5. Fit thermal space model 6. Fit HVAC model 7. Fit DHW model 8. Fit EV model 9. Fit generation system model 10. Retrieve environmental conditions 		
	D-SRI:		
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Calculate static SRI performance 2. Calculate dynamic building SRI performance 3. Send SRI score to Citizen App / UI 		
		Function	Responsible Component

Functional Dependencies	Retrieve raw data	Building Information Management Layer		
	Retrieve citizen profiles	Consumer Digital Twin		
	Retrieve metering/sensing data	Building Information Management Layer		
	Visualize results	Citizen App		
Non-functional Specifications	1. Secure handling of personal data			
	2. Automated periodic updating of models			
	3. One instance deployed per pilot building			
	4. Automated scheduling for periodic updates of the SRI metrics			
	5. Uninterrupted communication with other components of the CDT and the BIML for model and data retrieval.			
	6. One instance deployed per pilot building			
Implementation View				
Component Diagram	<p>The diagram illustrates the system architecture. A central orange box contains the Building Information Management (BIM) layer, which includes the Open Data Function Module (ODFM) and the Consumer Digital Twin (CDT). The CDT is composed of three sub-components: the Citizen Digital Twin (CiDT), the Building Digital Twin (BDT), and the Digital Smart Readiness Index (D-SRI). ODFM provides 'Profiling data, Building thermal model, DER models' to the CDT. The BIM layer interacts with external components: ECTs (Energy Community Tools) for 'Profiling data, Optimisation results' and 'Pricing data, Optimisation requests'; BIML (Building Information Management Layer) for 'Control actions' and 'IoT data, weather data'; and C-App (Citizen App) for 'Profiling data'.</p>			
	Interfaces/Data Requirements			
Input	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
	IoT data	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful
	Weather data	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful

	Optimisation requests	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	Profiling data	On Demand Flexibility Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Fitted building thermal model	On Demand Flexibility Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Fitted DER models	On Demand Flexibility Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Profiling data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Optimisation results	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Control actions	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Profiling data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful or AMQP

3.5. Community-level P2P Exchange Platform

General Information	
Component name	Community-level P2P exchange platform (P2P-EP)
Component Description	<p>The Community-level P2P exchange platform (P2P-EP) comprises two main components, the Energy/Flexibility Transactions (EFT) component and the Smart Contract Platform (SCP).</p> <p>The EFT is a blockchain based and smart contract enabled platform that will primarily facilitate the exchange of energy and flexibility among community members in a trustworthy and transparent manner. On a second level, the Platform will enable the execution of Smart Contracts to allow the delivery of energy and non-energy services to the community members.</p> <p>The SCP is a tool with a local database that allows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the creation of Smart Contracts based on predefined Service Level Agreements; • the Instantiation of Smart Contracts; and • the monitoring of Service Level Agreements related KPIs.
Interfaces with End-Users	None

Relevant UCs	UC7, UC8, UC9	
Lead Developing Partner	QUE	
Programming Languages	Go (with Java Plugins), RESTFul, Java, Rust	
Deployment Requirements	Linux based operational environment with min 1.5GHz, 64-bit quad-core processor, 2GB SDRAM memory and broad connectivity.	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	EFT:	
	1. Store Transaction Data	
	2. Check Balance of the user	
	3. Receive Smart Contract Results	
	4. Anonymize user	
	5. Receive Market related inputs	
	SCP:	
	1. Provide predefined SLAs and KPI description	
	2. Provide SLAs to authorized Service Providers	
	3. Create SLA – user bundles	
4. Save Complete SLAs		
5. Monitor SLA related KPIs		
6. Instantiate Smart Contracts		
7. Update Smart Contracts		
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Receive Market Inputs	Energy Community Tools
	Receive Energy Production/Consumption data	Building Information Management Layer
	Receive SLA – user bundles	Energy Community Tools
Update smart contracts	Building Asset Manager	
Non-functional Specifications	1. Scalability	
	2. Stability	
	3. Security	
Implementation View		

3.6. Citizen Application

The Citizen Application (C-App) includes both analytical and interfacing functionalities directed towards the building end-users. The C-App and its constituent modules are detailed below.

General Information	
Component name	Citizen Application (C-App)
Component Description	C-App is a User Interface (UI) app composed of four main value-adding modules that aim to facilitate citizens engagement and cover energy, smart living, wellbeing, collaboration, mobility, to name a few, domains, as they are briefly described below:

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Building Monitoring and Control module is responsible for processing all necessary information regarding the building facility and the citizen profiling. It is a module that provides a building smart-living experience to the citizen allowing him/her to monitor and control different building assets, remotely. 2. The Notification and Alerting system aims to populate and send notifications to the end-users about the operational status of the building, available energy assets (PV, EVⁱ, etc.), the energy community, detected anomalies/faults and other topics of interest. 3. The Collaboration Forum module provides a collaboration platform with several engagement tools and services. 4. Visual Analytics module is in charge of processing building IoT data and applying analytical reasoning techniques to enable (a) fast interpretation of past and present situations, (b) identification of possible alternative futures and issue of their warning and (c) decision making support. Anomaly detection mechanisms on energy consumption, cost will highlight any outlier cases and provide insight on how to avoid them in the future. 5. The Optimal Energy Schedule and Recommendation module aims to provide optimal recommendations to the end user regarding their energy consumption, energy efficiency, energy cost, use of available energy assets (PV, EV etc.) and DR participation.
Interfaces with End-Users	Yes / Consumer – Citizen
Relevant UCs	UC1, UC2, UC3, UC6, UC7, UC8
Lead Developing Partner	CERTH
Programming Languages	Python, Angular 9
Deployment Requirements	The application will be deployed as a web-based application along with a mobile version; the backend modules will run on an ubuntu server.
Specifications	
Functional Specifications	Building Monitoring and Control module:
	1. Display IoT data (sensing, metering, and monitoring)
	2. Display EV charging/discharging data
	3. Display user Profiling data (e.g., Comfort bounds, Occupancy, Energy asset flexibility)
	4. Monitoring of user preferences (e.g., Desired Comfort bounds, desired SoC bounds)
	5. Enable the building’s systems and energy assets remote control through the app
Notification and Alerting system:	
1. Notify end user about the approximate energy costs	

	2. Notify end user about optimal energy recommendations	
	3. Notify end user about detected anomalies	
	4. Notify end user about DR events/requests	
	5. Notify end user about relevant p2p transactions	
	6. Notify end user about energy community news/updates	
	7. Notify end user about security alerts	
	Visual Analytics module:	
	1. Apply analytical reasoning techniques	
	2. Translate data into a visible form that highlights important features	
	3. Display visual analytics data	
	4. Display billing data	
	Collaboration Forum module:	
	1. Allow the user to participate in individual topics of a collaboration forum	
	2. Provide an engagement platform that creates daily/weekly objectives for the user to ensure his/her engagement to the collaboration forum and energy community related processes (e.g., DR events etc.)	
	3. Incorporate a Reward system with ACCEPT points that could be translated to energy sales	
4. Display ranking statistics among at community level according to the end-users' ACCEPT points		
5. Display a Q&A table that contains general information about the functionality of this platform		
6. Display and monitor P2P transactions of the end user		
Optimal Energy Schedule and Recommendation module:		
1. Engage the user for potential savings		
2. Provide insights about the energy cost		
3. Provide forecasted estimated costs and recommendations		
4. Display recommendations of optimized solutions for energy efficiency considering comfort level.		
5. Display profit/penalties metrics in case that the user follows/deviates from the recommended schedule.		
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Retrieve building near real-time and historical IoT data and send control actions	Building Information Management Layer (BIML)
	Send optimisation requests and retrieve the results	Energy Community tools (Retailer, Aggregator, ESCo)
	Retrieve User Profiling data (e.g., Comfort bounds, Occupancy, EV charging/discharging)	Building Asset Manager (CiDT)
	Retrieve Knowledge, Pricing and DR related data	Energy Community Tools (Retailer, Aggregator)
	Retrieve Token balance data	Energy Community Tools
Non-functional	1. Availability-Component is continuous running	
	2. Performance-Service simultaneous users with a good response time	

Specifications	3. Scalability-Possibility to expand the system and avoid adversely affected performance
	4. Use-ability-Ease of use and user-friendly interface
	5. Responsiveness-Respond to a user’s input or an external event
	6. Security-Respect and protection of user’s privacy and security
	7. Extensibility- Possibility for new functional requirements addition

Implementation View

Interfaces/Data Requirements

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	IoT data	BIML	JSON	RESTful
	Profiling data	BAM	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	ECTs	JSON	RESTful
	DR alerts	ECTs	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	ECTs	JSON	RESTful
	Knowledge data	ECTs	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	ECTs	JSON	RESTful
	EV related data	DIML	JSON	MQTT
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	Control actions	BIML	JSON	AMQP
	Optimisation requests	ECTs	JSON	RESTful

3.7. Energy Community Tools – ECTs

The Energy Community Tools (ECTs) include all components that interface or support the business cases of the market actors and/or the energy communities. They comprise of two distinct set of tool suites, the horizontal ECTs and the vertical ECTs. The former include core modules, including optimisation and clustering engines, that are almost horizontally used by the vertical ECTs for the implementation of use cases and business scenarios. The latter are tools which are interchangeably by the energy communities of the project based on their assumed market role and implemented use cases.

The ECTs, apart from all the back-end components presented herein, will also be supported by User Interfaces (UIs) and Business Intelligence (BI) Suite, which will provide valuable, data-driven insights on the ACCEPT solution performance in through optimal visualisation aids for the community. In summary, the aforementioned suite will support the following:

- Provide visualisations, graphs and KPIs, supporting the user (in this case, the energy community as an aggregator, retailer, ESCo) in data-driven decision making.
- Support the user in extracting insights and discovering crucial points in speeding up the process and simultaneously improving the performance.
- Support the end users in initiating some of the UCs by exploiting their inputs. For example, the end users can request the optimization of day-ahead retail energy prices etc.

The main components comprising the Energy Community toolset are described below.

3.7.1. Horizontal Energy Community Tools – H-ECTs

General Information	
Component name	Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs)
Component Description	<p>The H-ECTs support all market role (i.e., aggregator, retailer and ESCo) specific functionalities of the Energy Community Tools. The H-ECTs consist of four main components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Virtual Power Plant (VPP) Manager is responsible for deciding on the optimal clustering of available assets of the community-level portfolio (VPP formulation and configuration) based on dynamic information received from the aggregator, retailer or ESCo tools. This dynamic information will refer to the optimisation context and scenarios required by each actor at a given time to cover community and/or grid needs. • The Demand Elasticity Estimator is responsible for estimating the optimal pricing signal at which prosumers within a community are most likely to respond to and provide flexibility services. • The Energy Community Flexibility Manager is the core community-level optimisation engine responsible for receiving optimisation requests from the aggregator, retailer and ESCo tools and translating them into certain flexibility /DR requests for specific prosumers and assets within the appropriately configured VPP. The responsibility of the specific component includes also the dispatch of such flexibility/DR requests to all relevant prosumers and assets within the community portfolio.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The P2P Supply Shadow Administrator is a tool that will stimulate community optimization through price signals. Taking into account implicit flexibility requests, electricity demand and supply within the community and the overall self-optimization strategy of the community, it will provide price signals to the prosumers in order to steer consumption. <p>The H-ECTs are also responsible for collecting all asset (both at building- and district-level) information (static and dynamic), as well as all flexibility forecasts generated by other ACCEPT solution components.</p>
Interfaces with End-users	None
Relevant UCs	UC4, UC5, UC6, UC7, UC8, UC9, UC10, UC11, UC12, UC13
Lead Developing Partner	Hypertech
Programming Languages	Python, Java
Deployment Requirements	Deployed as a cloud service
Specifications	
Functional Specifications	Virtual Power Plant Manager:
	1. Receive clustering criteria from the vertical energy community tools (i.e., the aggregator, retailer and ESCo tools)
	2. Create optimal VPPs for specific optimisation scenario based on the relevant VPP formulation criteria
	3. Send information on created optimal VPP to the Energy Community Flexibility Manager
	Demand Elasticity Estimator:
	1. Create consumers' elasticity regression models
	2. Estimate portfolio elasticity
	3. Forecast ideal demand curve at portfolio level and at prosumer level
	4. Calculate optimal energy retail prices
	5. Retrieve consumer's tariff data
	6. Retrieve wholesale market prices
	7. Monitor performance
	Energy Community Flexibility Manager:
1. Receive flexibility/DR request	
2. Retrieve optimal VPP information	

	3. Retrieve building-level optimisation results	
	4. Retrieve district-level optimisation results	
	5. Decide on DR requests per available prosumer and/or district-level asset	
	6. Dispatch DR requests	
	P2P Supply Shadow Administrator:	
	1. Retrieve Retailer electricity price	
	2. Retrieve Consumption and production optimization results	
	3. Calculate and dispatch P2P energy price	
	Generic functionalities:	
	1. Receive static building-level and district-level assets data	
2. Receive dynamic building-level and district-level assets data		
3. Receive building-level and district-level optimisation results (e.g., flexibility forecasts)		
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Collect building-level asset specifications	Building Information Management Layer
	Collect district-level asset specifications	District Information Management Layer
	Provision of Total Energy Surplus/Deficit	Energy Community Tools
	Collect wholesale energy price	ACCEPT Solution Emulator
	Collect DR requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator
	Collection of prosumer flexibility forecasts	Building Asset Manager
Collection of district asset flexibility forecasts	District Asset Manager	
Non-functional Specifications	1. Requires a scalable relational database	
	2. Suitable views for filtering assets	
	3. Handling of concurrent requests/ responses	
	4. Stability	
	5. Security	
Implementation View		

Interfaces/Data Requirements

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	DR requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Energy prices	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Building assets static data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Profiling data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Optimisation results	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecasts	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	SLAs	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Metering data	District Information Management Layer	JSON	MQTT
	Optimisation requests	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
Output	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
	Optimisation requests	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP

	Optimisation requests	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecasts	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Energy prices requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	Verification of response	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	DR alerts	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Knowledge data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful

3.7.2. ESCo Tools

General Information	
Component name	ESCo Tools (ETs)
Component Description	<p>The ETs suite consists of all functional level components addressing the needs of an ESCo (or an Energy Community acting as one). In summary, the tools will implement the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A portfolio-wide self-consumption (or self-balancing) optimization framework, • Communication with P2P supply chain to offer flexibility to third parties. • Continuous monitoring of the Energy Performance Contracting KPIs for all portfolio assets. • Amenity-as-a-Service offerings based on Service Level Agreements (SLAs).
Interfaces with End-users	None
Relevant UCs	UC2, UC3, UC5, UC7, UC12, UC13

Lead Developing Partner	Hypertech	
Programming Languages	Python, Java	
Deployment Requirements	Deployed as a cloud service	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	1. Receive DR request from the ACCEPT solution emulator	
	2. Translate DR request into optimisation scenario	
	3. Optimize community self-consumption	
	4. Optimize community self-balancing	
	5. Monitor building energy performance	
	6. Receive SLAs	
	7. Create compound service offerings for end customers	
	8. Translate optimisation scenario into clustering criteria for VPP manager	
	9. Translate optimisation scenario into optimisation constraints for Energy Community Flexibility Manager	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Flexibility Forecast	Building Asset Manager
	Flexibility Forecast	District Asset Manager
	Retrieve building asset static data	Building Information Management Layer
	Retrieve district asset static data	District Information Management Layer
	Monitor Performance	Building Asset Manager
Receive DR request	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	
Non-functional Specifications	1. Deployed as a cloud service	
	2. One instance per associated stakeholder	
Implementation View		

Interfaces/Data Requirements

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	DR requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Energy prices	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Building assets static data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Profiling data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Optimisation results	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecast requests	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	SLAs	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Metering data	District Information Management Layer	JSON	MQTT
	Optimisation requests	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol

Output	Optimisation requests	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Optimisation requests	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecasts	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Energy prices requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	Verification of response	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	DR alerts	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Knowledge data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful

3.7.3. Aggregator Tools

General Information	
Component name	Aggregator Tools (ATs)
Component Description	The ATs suite of tools includes all the computational engines that support the implementation of the explicit DR scenarios in the ACCEPT project, from the side of the aggregator.
Interfaces with End-users	None
Relevant UCs	UC8, UC10
Lead Developing Partner	Hypertech
Programming Languages	Python, Java

Deployment Requirements	Deployed as a cloud service	
Specifications		
Functional Specifications	1. Receive DR request from the ACCEPT solution emulator	
	2. Translate DR request into optimisation scenario	
	3. Translate optimisation scenario into clustering criteria for VPP manager	
	4. Translate optimisation scenario into optimisation constraints for Energy Community Flexibility Manager	
	5. Retrieve building flexibility timeseries	
	6. Accumulate flexibility	
	7. Disaggregate requested consumption modification to buildings, EVs, district assets	
	8. Disaggregate requested consumption to different buildings	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	Forecast Flexibility	Flexibility Forecast Collection
	Retrieve assets	Community Asset Portfolio Registry
	Monitor event	Portfolio Monitoring and Control Dispatch
Non-functional Specifications	1. Deployed as a cloud service	
	2. One instance per associated stakeholder	
Implementation View		
Component Diagram	<p>The diagram illustrates the system architecture. On the left, the ASE (Accept Solution Emulator) sends DR requests and energy prices to ESCO, Retailer, and Aggregator. ESCO and Retailer send energy prices requests and verification of response back to ASE. In the center, ESCO and Retailer are grouped under ECTS (Energy Community Flexibility Manager). Aggregator is also connected to ECTS. On the right, H-ECTs (Home Energy Control Technology) interacts with several external components: BAM (Building Asset Manager) for pricing data and optimization requests; DAM (District Asset Manager) for optimization requests and PV generation forecasts; P2P-EP (Peer-to-Peer Energy Platform) for pricing data and optimization results; DIML (District Metering Layer) for metering data; and C-App (Community Application) for DR alerts, pricing data, knowledge data, optimization results, and token balance. Optimization requests are also sent from H-ECTs to C-App.</p>	
	Interfaces/Data Requirements	

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	DR requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Energy prices	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Building assets static data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Profiling data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Optimisation results	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecast requests	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	SLAs	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Metering data	District Information Management Layer	JSON	MQTT
	Optimisation requests	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	Optimisation requests	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Optimisation requests	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecasts	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Energy prices requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	Verification of response	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful

	DR alerts	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Knowledge data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful

3.7.4. Retailer Tools

General Information	
Component name	Retailer Tools (RTs)
Component Description	The RTs suite supports the Energy retailer role of the community services, by providing portfolio-wide management for dynamic pricing scenarios, as well as billing information for end customers.
Interfaces with End-users	None
Relevant UCs	UC4, UC7, UC9, UC11
Lead Developing Partner	Witside, Hypertech
Programming Languages	Python, Java
Deployment Requirements	Deployed as a cloud service
Specifications	
Functional Specifications	1. Receive DR request from the ACCEPT solution emulator
	2. Translate DR request into optimisation scenario
	3. Translate optimisation scenario into clustering criteria for VPP manager
	4. Translate optimisation scenario into optimisation constraints for Energy Community Flexibility Manager
	5. Retrieve wholesale market prices
	6. Retrieve weather data
	7. Retrieve alternative energy source data
	8. Estimate portfolio elasticity
	9. Forecast portfolio demand curve
	10. Calculate optimal energy retail prices
Function	Responsible Component

Functional Dependencies	Estimate consumer elasticity	Demand Elasticity Estimator
	Energy consumption measurements for prosumers	Building Information Management Layer
Non-functional Specifications	Deployed as a cloud service	

Implementation View

Interfaces/Data Requirements

	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	DR requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Energy prices	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Weather data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Alternative energy source data	External third-party sources	JSON	RESTful
	Oil/Gas prices	External third-party sources	JSON	RESTful
	Coal consumption	External third-party sources	JSON	RESTful
	Metering IoT data	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful
	Building assets static data	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful
	Profiling data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP

	Optimisation requests	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Optimisation results	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	SLAs	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	Optimisation requests	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP
	Optimisation requests	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	PV generation forecasts	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Energy prices requests	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	Verification of response	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful
	DR alerts	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Pricing data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Knowledge data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful
	Token balance	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful

3.7.5. Business Intelligence Tool

General Information	
Component name	Business Intelligence Tool
Component Description	The Business Intelligence Tool combines data from each participating energy community on their energy consumption, generation, applicable energy prices, emissions for some energy resources such as gas, solar, wind, etc., to produce meaningful contextual information for the community.
Interfaces with End-users	Yes / Energy communities
Relevant UCs	None
Lead Developing Partner	Witside
Programming Language	SQL
Deployment Requirements	Deployed as a cloud service
Specifications	

Functional Specifications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Retrieve data from the four sites throughout the year (over a year) + time (during an hour) 2. Total consumption data for the whole community 3. Consumption data for EWH (electric water heater) in kWh 4. Consumption data for HVAC (heating, ventilation and air-conditioning) in kWh 5. Consumption data for EV (electric vehicles) in kWh 6. Total generation data for Photovoltaics in kWh (for the whole community) 7. Retrieve dynamic prices schemes for implicit demand response 8. Energy Prices by day 9. CO2 Emissions (gas, coal, wind, hydro, solar) amount (gCO₂eq/kWh) 10. Forecast energy for consumption (planned) 11. Forecast energy for generation (scheduled) 	
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component
	-	-
Non-functional Specifications	Deployed as a cloud service	

Interfaces/Data Requirements				
	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	Energy prices	ACCEPT Solution Emulator	JSON	RESTful
	EWH consumption data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	HVAC consumption data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	EV consumption data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	Solar generation data	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful
	CO2 Emissions for gas, coal, hydro, solar, wind	Third-party system	JSON	RESTful

	Building assets static data	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful
	Optimisation results	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful

3.8. ACCEPT solution emulator – ASE (CIRCE)

General Information	
Component name	ACCEPT solution emulator (ASE)
Component Description	<p>The ASE is the component responsible for emulating the role of external to the energy community energy stakeholders, such as the DSO and the energy market operator. The ASE consists of two sub-components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The DSO emulator, which is responsible for dynamically assessing the grid state (through appropriate simulations/power flow analysis) and issuing demand response /flexibility requests to the energy communities, i.e., triggering the ACCEPT digital toolset. • The Energy Market emulator, which is responsible for estimating/forecasting and communicating wholesale energy prices to the respective actors within ACCEPT, namely the energy community as an aggregator, retailer and ESCo.
Interfaces with End-users	Energy community
Relevant UCs	UC4, UC8, UC10, UC11
Lead Developing Partner	CIRCE
Programming Languages	Java, Python
Deployment Requirements	Cloud Based. Availability of DSO historical data which can be used for simulation of grid state.
Specifications	
Functional Specifications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Retrieve DSO historical data 2. Estimate electricity grid state 3. Estimate flexibility needs based on electricity grid state 4. Create compound DR request based on estimated flexibility needs for grid constraint alleviation

5. Forecast energy wholesale prices				
Functional Dependencies	Function	Responsible Component		
	Retrieve DSO historical data	External legacy system		
Non-functional Specifications	-			
Implementation View				
Component Diagram				
Interfaces/Data Requirements				
	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	DSO historical data	External legacy system	JSON	RESTful
	Price request	Energy Community Tools	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Verification of response	Energy Community Tools	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	DR requests	Energy Community Tools	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful
	Energy prices	Energy Community Tools	JSON	AMQP, MQTT or RESTful

3.9. Lessons learned

The main lessons learned included herein stem from and concern the process of designing the ACCEPT system, detailing its architecture and defining the specifications of its main components and the interfaces among them. They are summarised below:

- It is important that the use cases are revisited throughout the process of the design and development of a project’s main technical solutions, as interactions among and technical / functional specifications of components help refining the use cases and making them easier to implement during the demonstration phase.
- There is a great need to follow an agile rather than a waterfall approach⁶ for the definition, design and development of the technical solutions / system components of a project. This facilitates the integration

⁶ A waterfall approach is based on the development of various system components independently from one another. It is a top-down sequential execution of activities with a planning phase where requirements for

of the various components into the final, integrated solution. Within ACCEPT, a hybrid approach was followed (mainly due to time constraints) for the development of the various ACCEPT modules, based on a series of technical workshops among the project's technical providers, where interfacing needs were teased out and the interactions between the modules were collectively agreed, but then the development of the modules was carried out quite independently. As a result, integration of the various system components was more challenging than it would have been should a robust agile methodology have been followed (with regular development checkpoints defined for partial technical solution validation).

- Based on the aforementioned point, the consortium strongly encourages the organisation of technical workshops for the definition, design and development of technical solutions within a project. Focused / surgery sessions among all technical providers of a project help identify early within the process development needs with regards to interfaces and solution data requirements, which is a valuable step towards a smoother integration phase.

system components are gathered, the system architecture is designed and implemented, and then tests on individual components are performed.

4. Conclusions

This document details the software architecture of the ACCEPT system architecture, as well as the specifications of its components. All technical partners associated with developing part of the solution, were asked to fill in a characterization table for each component, providing the functional and non-functional specifications, highlighting interdependencies with other components, and declaring the input/output data requirements.

Additionally, detailed component diagrams were created, and finally, the connection with D2.1 was performed via a mapping of components to Use Cases that required relevant functionalities. The collected material was integrated and two rounds of updates followed, in order to consolidate and bring in line the various inputs. During this process, it was ensured that data and functional specifications between the components were harmonised, and that the offered functionalities satisfy the end-user requirements and use cases defined in D2.1. The deliverable also contains a mapping of the high-level architecture to the SGAM model, in order to assist to future integration and development activities.

This is the second and last version of the ACCEPT system architecture. It provides an update of the first version following engagements with pilot partners and users and a refinement of their requirements. Eventual updates will be included in the next versions of the deliverables that focus on the development of the components of the ACCEPT solution.

Annex I – Component’s Specifications and Requirements Template

Table 1. Component's Specifications and Requirements Template

General Information				
Component name	<i>Component name as shown in the system architecture (if modified, changes should be propagated there)</i>			
Component Description	<i>Short textual description of the Component (objective, functionalities, etc.)</i>			
Interfaces with End-users	<i>End-users interacting with the component if any</i>			
Relevant UCs	<i>UCs in which the component will need to be used (provide the ID of each such UC)</i>			
Lead Developing Partner	<i>Partner developing the component and its sub-components</i>			
Programming Language(s)	<i>Which programming languages will be used for the development</i>			
Deployment Requirements	<i>Software and hardware requirements for deploying the solution to the pilot sites</i>			
Specifications				
Functional Specifications	<i>The functions that the component needs to offer (Taken out of the shared excel sheet)</i>			
Functional Dependencies	Function		Responsible Component	
	<i>Functions that should be provided by other components in order to implement all functionalities listed above</i>		<i>Component responsible for implementing the respective functionality</i>	
Non-functional Specifications	<i>Specifications related to security, performance, reliability, data granularity, scheduling, etc.</i>			
Implementation View				
Component Diagram	<i>UML component diagram showing the sub-components of the component and interfaces to other components (Do not skip the second part, it is important)</i>			
Interfaces/Data Requirements				
	Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Input	<i>Input data required by the component to</i>	<i>Component that provides the data</i>	<i>Format of exchanged information (e.g., JSON)</i>	<i>Communication protocol (e.g., HTTP RESTful, AMQP)</i>

	<i>implement a functionality</i>			
	Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol
Output	<i>Output data generated by the component as a result of a function</i>	<i>Component that requests the data</i>	<i>Format of exchanged information (e.g., JSON)</i>	<i>Communication protocol (e.g., HTTP RESTful, AMQP)</i>

ⁱ Regarding the C-App functionalities, they have been already described in detail as can be seen in Deliverable D5.5. They have been developed and configured in a horizontal manner, taking into consideration the needs and capabilities of all the project pilots as seen at the time, for example considering residential EV chargers. In case of any updates received from the pilots these will be further described in the next version of the deliverable, that is D5.6, due in February 2023.